

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN USULUT-TAFSIR, TA'WIL AND TAFSIR

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Before defining the science of "Usulut Tafsir", let's explain the words "usul" and "tafsir". "Usul" is an Arabic word, and "asl" means the basis, foundation of things. The lexical meaning of the word "tafsir" is to interpret and explain something, and in the term it is said to explain the meanings of the Holy Quran in detail. Based on these two definitions, the science of "Usulut Tafsir" is defined as "the set of rules and basic concepts by which the interpretation of the word of Allah is learned and referred to when a disagreement arises." If we pay attention to the definitions, it becomes clear that the science of "Usulut Tafsir" is only a collection of rules for studying the meanings of the verses of the Holy Quran. The science of "Quranic sciences" is a general science that studies various aspects of the history of the Quran, its grammatical aspects, rules of recitation, and interpretation. In fact, the science of methods of interpretation developed as a part of the science of Quranic sciences, and later separate books were written on this subject. When talking about the difference between them, we are not talking about other sciences, but about the specific aspects of the main part of one science.

The history of Quranic sciences, the science of interpretation, like all Islamic sciences, dates back to the time of our Prophet Muhammad Mustafa, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him, and the companions. Our Prophet, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him, used to interpret and explain to his companions the verses that were difficult for them to understand. We can understand this from the following incident: When the verse "Those who believe and do not mix their faith with oppression (shirk) - those are the ones who are secure and they are the ones who are guided" was revealed, the companions said, "No one wrongs himself,

O Messenger of Allah." That is, they could not understand what exactly was meant by the word "oppression" in the verse. Then the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) interpreted the word "oppression" and said that it meant shirk and said, "Have you not read that Allah Almighty said, "Indeed, shirk is a great injustice?"

The period of formation of the science of "Quranic sciences" and its emergence in the form of books fell much later than the science of hadith. The second century of the Hijri is considered the period of the development of the science of hadith. In this century, hadith collections began to be compiled into book form by hadith scholars. Although they also included knowledge related to interpretation, they could not be considered a separate step in Quranic studies or exegesis. Some scholars became famous for collecting hadiths related to the interpretation of the Holy Quran. Examples of this include Yazid ibn Harun al-Sulami (d. 117 AD) and Shu'bah ibn Hajjaj(d.160AD),may Godhav emercyon him.The science of "Quranic sciences" began to take shape as a separate science in the third century AH. Among the first to write books on the terminology of the Holy Quran were Ali ibn Madani (teacher of Imam Bukhari, d. 234 AD), Abu Ubayd al-Qasim ibn Sullam (d. 224 AD), and Ibn Qutaybah (d. 276 AD). In the fourth century AH, Muhammad ibn Khalaf ibn Marzban (d. 309 AD), Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Qasim al-Anbari (d. 328 AD), and Abu Bakr Sijistani (d. 330 AD) wrote books on the science. In the following centuries, the majority of works on this science began to be published.

The word "ta'wil" means "return" in the dictionary. In terminology, it is the twisting of the meaning of a word and its transformation from the first meaning that comes to mind to a different meaning or from a strong meaning to a weak meaning. If that twisting and transformation is with evidence, it is a correct interpretation, otherwise it is a corrupted interpretation. The interpretation of the truth that the word returns to is called ta'wil (i.e. the truth that is intended from the

word is called ta'wil. Transl.). The interpretation of a message is the same as the message that was given. The interpretation of an order is the same as the act that was commanded. This is similar to the following meaning that was given by Aisha (may Allah be pleased with her): "The Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) used to interpret the Qur'an while bowing, saying: 'Subhanakallahumma Rabbana wa bihamdika, Allahumma aigfir li'." That is, he would carry out the order given in the Qur'an. Allah the Almighty says: Are they waiting except for its interpretation? On the Day when its interpretation comes, those who forgot it before will say: "When the messengers of our Lord came with the truth..." (Surah Al-A'raf, verse 53).

That is, "On the Day when the truth and confirmation of the word of Allah come."

The concept of ta'wil in the words of the commentators: This is interpreting the word to see if it corresponds to its meaning or not, and explaining its meaning. This is a well-known term.